

Reflections on Trust and Confidence in Climate Science and Climate Action

Survey of data source - Interim

Martin Jukes, 14th February, 2025.

The NetDRIVE project (Jukes and Sparrow, 2025) identifies the need for trust to empower the community to negotiate the transformational change to net zero. There are many indications that academic institutions and society as a whole are finding it hard to maintain let alone build trust. This note surveys some of the lines of discussion to be pursued in the academic literature. It is a huge topic: these notes provide some markers to orientate discussion.

The importance of reciprocal trust in the 21st century comes out clearly in the literature cited below, with the equally important caveat that there are many modalities and sources of trust that will need to be respected in our inclusive network. We also need to consider how much trust we want in terms of the scope of trust we can accept as individuals and as a community.

At the same time the pace of change in both digital infrastructure and the disruptive artificial intelligence applications multiplying within it is creating concerns about erosion of trust in our information environment (Bengio et al., 2025, p. 69).

Data is too limited to provide clear evidence on trends in trust. The perception that there are conflicting sources of information, even when climate scientists are trusted, could be a barrier to progress.

Is there a crisis in trust?

Trust is vital in our academic world and in the communities that we live in. Angela Merkel (2021), reflecting on the years of the COVID pandemic, put it succinctly: "The last two years of the pandemic in particular have brought into clear focus how important trust in politics, science and social discourse is – and how fragile this trust can be." The NetDRIVE project aims to "Build trust and confidence in our transition to a sustainable DRI by 2040 or sooner" (Jukes and Sparrow, 2025): this note looks at some of the issues we can expect to encounter.

Baert and Shipman (2005) review challenges facing European academic institutions and conclude that problems arise from the public taking a more critical view of a “once highly exclusive system”. They discuss challenges to the Humboldtian model of a university as a body of “self-governing professionals, accountable to and monitored by itself,” including a broad body of academic work pointing towards a role as enablers of knowledge discovery rather than donnish deliverers of knowledge. More recently, Seyd (2024) has reviewed trust trends in Britain and finds indications of declining trust in political institutions and experts. Seyd also counsils against placing too much trust in the limited metrics available.

Baert and Shipman do not comment on climate science specifically but do have a reference to the way that lack of clear conclusions undermines confidence in natural sciences. This is countered, generally, by the ability to deliver useful information.

Cologna et al. (2024) review data on trust in climate science and scientists, drawing on data from the World Economic Forum (WEF, 2022) Climate Progress Survey and from other sources. The WEF survey shows generally high levels of trust in climate science and positive trends over the 3 years (2019-2021) for which they have data. Optimism about reducing emissions is mixed, very low in Western Europe and high in South Asia. Believe in personal responsibility for addressing climate change is also relatively low in Western Europe, with 59% expressing themselves as “Extremely/Very Responsible for Addressing Climate Change Individually” compared with 76% in South Asia. However, the number of respondents worldwide who felt little or no personal responsibility was very low at 9%.

In the UK, the Department for Energy Security and Net Zero (DESNZ, formerly BEIS) has tracked public attitudes. There is a change in the questions used in 2021: the pre-2021 surveys do not include explicit questions on trust. Since 2021 questions on air travel and consumption of meat have been dropped, questions on recycling and food waste have been brought in. The DESNZ (2021) report covers the period 2012 to 2021 and shows increasing concern about climate change. The latest report (DESNZ, 2024) covers three years, 2021-2023. It shows high levels of trust, but also shows that many people are concerned about conflicting sources of information.

The HMG (2003) white paper on the future of higher education does not deal explicitly with trust and instead focusses on the need to respond to foreign competition and reverse years of underinvestment. Trow (2006) provides a different perspective which is not comfortable reading for those who pride themselves on working in progressive institutions embedded in their communities. In particular, he highlights his surprise at the lack of “friends” of the sector in the UK, the people who not only want something from universities but also want to support them. From Trow’s perspective the problem is not primarily funding but about how the sector engages with the world, a view which matches the conclusions of Baert and Shipman noted above.

Robust data is limited: Figure 1 shows some relevant metrics. Interpersonal trust in the UK, as measured by the World Values Survey (Figure 1a), dipped in 2000-2005 but has since recovered and moved slightly above levels recorded in the 1980s. Looking at how interpersonal trust varies around the world we see nothing unusual about the UK position: trust levels are in line with our geographic and cultural neighbours (Figure 1b).

Beall et al. (2017) look at the impact of climate scientists acting as advocates on public trust using a sample of 2,435 US adults. They conclude that there can be a positive impact when the advocacy is on uncontroversial topics, but negative impact when controversy is involved.

Figure 1: Results on interpersonal trust from the World Values Survey. (a) Share of people in the UK who agree with the statement "most people can be trusted" against year of survey, from 1984 to 2022, (b) Share of people agreeing as in (a) for different countries plotted against GDP per capita, for the most recent survey year, 2022.

What do we mean by trust?

Trust makes many things simpler, but it is not a simple concept to define or an easy target to attain. A blog post by Power (2022) gives a good overview of the difference between trust in the data science ("an intrinsic and core construct within contracts, regulation and code ") and trust among people and organisations (an important synthetic force which "which encompasses values such as reciprocity, solidarity and cooperation").

Pritchard (2022) reviews the impact of COVID on trust in British Higher Education Institutions. The distinctions between interpersonal, social, institutional, and political trust are discussed: these categories of trust are not mutually exclusive and may co-exist. Two main bases of trust are rational-instrumental trust, flowing from authority and standards, and normative-cognitive trust derived from shared values and beliefs. The former is sometimes discussed in terms of anchors of trust, or gatekeepers. In the past the anchors might have taken the form of watermarked paper or a seal. This form of trust has been important for academics in the recent past: the confidence placed in them by a university conveyed a status which ensured a degree of trust. All European Academies (ALLEA) (2018) and Trow (2005) convey the impression that the trust anchorage provided by universities is slipping and social norms shift towards the more fluid environment of normative-cognitive trust.

The interdependence of trustor and trustee is highlighted by Pritchard and also by Van der Werff et al. (2019) who look at one

consequence of this interdependence in the form of extrinsic motivation of trust: that is, decisions to assign trust because of expected benefits rather than as a consequence of intrinsic qualities of the object of trust.

The interdependence between those placing and receiving trust is also discussed by Quéré (2001), who also highlights the ternary nature of trust: it is not just a question of who is trusted but of what they are trusted in or with: “A trusts B in/with X”. Changing trust in academia is inextricably linked to the changing role of academia. This will be made particularly challenging by the fact that “X”, the article of trust, is likely to be synthetic: if we work purely in the realm of trust derived from rational-instrumental trust anchors we can define the scope of the trust explicitly, but working in the realm of normative-cognitive trust we don't have this freedom.

All European Academies (ALLEA) (2018) discuss sources of trust. They conclude that “important that we protect science as a societal institution by holding on to the demands of integrity, transparency, independence, and accountability whilst reinvesting in science’s moral economy,” noting the risk that excessive regulation can undermine trust. ALLEA also reflect on the need for further action and consideration in many areas, including gaining a better understanding of how we and others assign trust. They also note the difficulty of convincing others that our work is trustworthy when we have different measures of trustworthiness in different fields.

White et al (2024) note that consistency, which is often considered as a source of trust, can undermine trust if it is seen to signify lack of qualities such as mercy and discretion. ALLEA (op. Cit.) also comment on the negative impact of high

Trust is also heavily influenced by subconscious factors (e.g. Nieuwenburg et al., 2019 discuss the role of odour). It is important to be aware of these subconscious factors and to ensure that we understand where we are putting trust and what we are asking of others.

What is the impact of trust?

Hall et al. (2018) find that in their study (600 US adults interviewed 7 times over the course of 12 months) skepticism towards the science was correlated with positive personal behaviour such as use of public transport, purchasing eco-friendly products and preference, for reusable shopping bags. Those who believed in the climate science had greater support for policy based solutions.

Related Information

The United Nations Development Programme has run the People's Climate Vote in 2020 and 2023 to gather information about public support for action on climate change, but does not deal with trust directly. UNDP (2024) shows that climate change is increasingly on people's minds and is having an impact on big life decisions. The UNDP (2020) report showed low support for meat-free diets (around 30%) and high support for waste reductions in food and domestic heating.

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